

Manifesto

of the

“Italian Data Steward Community”

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This is the English version of the [“Manifesto della Comunità Italiana Data Stewards”](#).
Translation by Manuel Ciccarelli (UNIMORE).

1. Premises

Research data is one of the fundamental components on which scientific discoveries are based. For this reason, it must be preserved and, whenever possible, made publicly accessible to ensure that science remains open, reproducible, transparent, and reliable. Furthermore, technological advancements have greatly increased the ability to generate and acquire data, making it essential not only to access data but also to learn how to collect, manage, and analyze it properly and effectively while respecting ethical and legal principles.

In the vision of the European Commission (and beyond) data is at the heart of innovation and research, playing a crucial role in addressing major future challenges such as climate change, sustainable economies and mass epidemics – also thanks to the recent developments in the field of Artificial Intelligence.

In this scenario, it is essential to support researchers in producing high-quality, machine-readable data that is FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) for both humans and machines. It is therefore clear how crucial it is for universities and research institutions to commit to training and hiring Data Stewards and other professionals skilled in research data management, recognizing them as an integral part of their research support activity.

Given this international context, the Italian Data Steward Community (CIDS) was established also thanks to the role of its members within the [ICDI \(Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure\)](#) working group and the European project [Skills4EOSC – “Skills for the European Open Science Commons: creating a training ecosystem for Open and FAIR science”](#).

2. Who We Are

The [Italian Data Steward Community \(CIDS\)](#) brings together specialists in research data management in Italy who identify with the role of Data Steward, regardless of the official classification they have within their respective institutions.

In this manifesto, we define a Data Steward as *“someone who possesses and applies the necessary skills to manage and enhance research data, ensuring its maximum usability by the scientific*

community and society while safeguarding the rights and legitimate interests of all involved parties." Furthermore, the Data Steward serves as a facilitator in the relations between researchers and those responsible for research data infrastructures and services.

In 2023 the ICDI, coordinator of the European project Skills4EOSC, in collaboration with the University of Bologna, GARR and Italian Technology Institute, conducted a survey to map the presence of professionals supporting data management within Italian universities and research institutions and to propose the creation of a national sharing group. The need for peer exchange and specialized training, along with the desire for recognition of the Data Steward profession, were the main motivations behind the creation of the Italian Data Steward Community (CIDS), which held its first meeting in Rome on November 7th, 2023.

3. Purpose of the Community

The mission of CIDS is to support, promote and enhance the role of Data Stewards in Italy. It is committed to creating a recognized, sustainable professional community based on cooperation and training. CIDS aims to consolidate existing skills and experiences in the field to encourage the spread of best practices for effective, ethical research data management founded on FAIR principles. Through its actions and initiatives, CIDS is dedicated to ensuring that the essential support role provided by Data Stewards in universities, research institutions and research infrastructures is recognized, strengthened and valued.

Strategic Objectives

To create opportunities for sharing and developing new skills

CIDS offers opportunities and tools to enrich professional expertise. It promotes the creation of spaces for discussion, both within the community and with other national and international entities, fostering the acquisition and consolidation of specialized knowledge that is not always available in traditional training paths.

To support the adoption of best practices for research data management

CIDS promotes the sharing and exchange of individual or group experiences, solutions, tools, ideas and best practices for implementing FAIR principles and sharing research results across different disciplines, highlighting concrete examples from both within and outside the community.

To increase awareness of the role of Data Steward

CIDS aims to raise awareness of the importance of the Data Steward role, both among those who already hold this position to strengthen their professional identity, and by sensitizing the scientific community as well as the public. This will highlight its strategic importance for creating a more open and collaborative research ecosystem. For this purpose, CIDS regularly participates in national and international events to disseminate its founding values, raise awareness of the Data Steward role and present the community, its objectives and activities.

4. Organization of CIDS and Participation Methods

In line with the spirit that has characterized the community from the beginning, voluntary, active, collaborative, inclusive and respectful participation is promoted for all members.

Each participant in CIDS (as defined in paragraph 2. "Who We Are") commits to participating, based on their capabilities, at an individual level and free of charge, in initiatives organized by CIDS and/or to proposing new activities and topics of interest.

Based on these premises, participants can engage in CIDS activities at various levels of involvement:

Subscription to the mailing list

Those who simply wish to stay updated on CIDS initiatives and share events or activities of common interest can submit a request to join the mailing list (distribution list) at the email address data-stewards@lists.icdi.it.

Participation in Workspaces

Those who wish to participate more actively in the work of CIDS can request, via the mailing list, to join the workspaces and collaboration environments (virtual research environment) adopted. In the email concerning your request some basic information must be included - such as education or qualifications, affiliation institution, role within the institution, type of support provided at the institution - to complete a short "personal profile" that will be shared with other participants. The purpose is to create a registry of active Data Stewards within CIDS. Participants in the workspaces are encouraged to contribute, from a perspective of collaboration and sharing, to the activities of the Working Groups (WG) and the Coordination Group (CG).

Participation in Working Groups (WG)

The Working Groups drive the actions of the community, with each group focusing on a single activity or initiative. A WG can be temporary or permanent, requiring either occasional or more structured involvement based on the specific activity.

Any participant in CIDS can propose the creation of a new WG or request to join an existing one. The formation of a new WG is discussed within the Coordination Group (CG) before being officially activated. Each WG must have at least four participants and be coordinated by at least one chairperson. The chairperson is responsible for coordinating the group's activities throughout its duration and for producing the predefined outcomes, which must be made available to CIDS and, when possible, to the public. The chairs of the WG automatically become members of the CG for the duration of their work, which requires participation in periodic CG meetings.

Participation in the Coordination Group (CG)

The Coordination Group (CG) is the permanent working group tasked with maintaining an overview of the Community and coordinating the activities carried out by the various WGs. The CG is composed of the chairs of the active WGs, who take on the responsibility of participating in the organization and coordination activities of the community. The Coordination Group is led by at least two chairs, who may also be external to the WGs, and who volunteer to be appointed with their nomination subject to approval by the CG members.